

ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' BASIC KNOWLEDGE OF THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *This article outlines important aspects of developing basic family knowledge in modern young people, the pedagogical requirements for young people who want to start a family, and the development of basic knowledge of the family.*

Keywords: *family, youth, upbringing, values, basic knowledge, pedagogical requirements.*

Family is considered a social institution, it is a place of initial socialization for a person. The family moves the society, the individuals in it are subject to all the rules, laws, and principles of the society and, in turn, participate in their development.

American psychologist Virginia Satir says: "Family is a microcosm of the whole world. It is enough to study the family to understand it. Family power, confidentiality, independence, trust, communication skills are the key to many events in life. If we want to change the world, we need to change the family" [1].

So, emphasizing once again the importance of the family in personal education, it is important to pay more attention to family education in today's violent times, to teach young people to appreciate the family, especially to teach young people who are studying in the pedagogical field the meaning of family pedagogy.

All good intentions, virtues, values, love of country, respect for parents, hard work, generosity etc. in a person are first formed in the family. The Uzbek family preserves centuries-old strong spiritual values and passes them on to future generations. If there is a healthy atmosphere in the family and good relationships between adults, the young generation who are brought up in such families will undoubtedly grow up to be people who honor their parents, respect the elders, and have a pure heart and language. Every parent who is lucky enough to have a child wants to show their child endless love, to be proud of their work and achievements, and to be a loyal citizen of their country. Parents want their child to be knowledgeable, to follow the path of enlightenment and to work honestly, and they work tirelessly in this regard and strive to give their child a decent education.

Today, teaching the young generation to love their parents and the Motherland by raising them in the spirit of family values, and using the example of parents and adults to educate them in such qualities as hard work and humanity, is an urgent pedagogical problem. Especially, the issue of formation of collective knowledge about the family among the youth of today is a responsible task for the state, society, neighborhood and education system, and parents.

Complex-(Arabic), collection; collect, a whole thing; category. [2]

The information created by scientists about the phenomena of nature and society, the reflection of reality in human thinking. [3]

Collective knowledge about the family is a collection of historical, legal, economic, social, psychological-pedagogical and other information and knowledge about the family collected and grouped together.

One of the Russian research scientists, A.V. Petrov, while studying the value orientations of young people, shows that they have a lack of psychological knowledge and skills related to the family: "The study of the value orientations of young people shows that the family is the youth remains the main value for Young people want the support of their parents in the family in the process of socialization, and they are ready to build a family based on humanistic and moral principles in the future, but they lack psychological knowledge and skills related to the family".[4] Today, young people have very shallow understanding and knowledge about family and family values. For this reason, it is one of the important tasks in the pedagogical process to create collective knowledge about the family and to make them understand that the family is a value. After all, thanks to the family, continuity of generations is ensured and nations preserve their nationality. Also, the process of birth of healthy children will take place in the society, the reproductive health of the population will be strengthened, and a healthy lifestyle will be stable among people.

Having studied the available sources, we divided the collective knowledge about the family into the following types:

Types of collective knowledge about the family:

- Pedagogical and psychological knowledge;
- Legal knowledge;
- Physiological knowledge;
- Economic knowledge;
- Political and social knowledge.

Collective knowledge about this family is extensive, and young people who are going to get married must have special knowledge about them. At the same time, young people who want to start a family should follow the following pedagogical requirements:

- they can imagine the optimal model of the future family;
- to have the ability to design housing and economic support;
- existence of a desire to give birth to healthy children and raise them, provide economic support;
- understanding that mutual respect between family members and mutual cooperation in the family community is important;
- to know the importance of dedication, loyalty and kindness for the family;
- emotional-psychological closeness between family members, understanding that spiritual and moral views should be compatible, etc.

Therefore, according to these requirements, it is worth noting that students in higher education institutions should not only have knowledge and skills related to professional activities, but also general knowledge related to each young family.

In our opinion, the acquisition of collective knowledge about the family by young people leads to a decrease in the family crisis.

According to the observations and questionnaires, there are the following problems in the preparation of young people for family in the process of higher education:

- the education system of our country does not have specific directions for preparing young people for family life;
- Pedagogical models of the process of family training of young people have not been developed;

- practical-methodical work was not carried out in the cooperation of pedagogues, psychologists, physiologists, economists in family training of young people:
- knowledge about gender equality issues is not sufficiently formed in the minds of young people;
- in preparing young people for family life, no specific tasks have been defined between educational institutions and the family, neighborhood.

In our opinion, it is necessary to pay attention to the following important aspects in the formation of collective knowledge about the family in young people:

- strengthening individual work with young people on family matters;
- elimination of their problems based on attracting young people to psychological counseling centers;
- determining their value orientations by organizing a club of students with families;
- development of comprehensive support mechanisms for young families receiving education;
- didactically correct selection of educational material for the family pedagogy course;
- organization of integrative courses of family pedagogy and other subjects, etc.

The above points show that in the process of social life, especially in the family, young people absorb family values and learn to follow them at an early age. At the same time, these values serve to educate young people's loyalty to family and marriage, loyalty to love.

In short, in higher education institutions, students should acquire not only knowledge and skills related to professional activities, but also general knowledge related to each young family. In the process of social life, especially in the family, young people should learn family values and learn to follow them.

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